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RESULTS OF EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES OF A POTATO GROOMER MOTOBLOCK

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Abstract

The article presents the problems of mechanization of work in small-circuit areas for the cultivation of vegetables and potatoes, the general view of the potato digger and its agrotechnical indicators. The world is introducing mechanization of potato harvesting with the help of potato harvesters, which can reduce labor costs by 3-5 times. Due to soil and climatic features (high summer temperatures, low relative air humidity, soil compaction after irrigation), potato harvesters are not widely used in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Therefore, the potato crop is harvested with the participation of numerous pickers for the manual selection of tubers and loaders. Therefore, scientific research is required to develop a more efficient method of harvesting tubers that provides the required quality of work at lower energy costs and greater productivity. To solve this problem, an energy-saving potato digger has been developed that reduces the loss and damage to potato tubers.

Keywords: Motoblock, potato digger, potatoes, frame, landing, speed.

In the Republic, due to the lack of small-scale mechanization for working in small-circuit areas, many operations for the cultivation of vegetables and potatoes are carried out manually, which is associated with an increase in labor and material costs. In developed foreign countries, when growing food crops

in small-circuit household plots, mobile small-scale mechanization tools are widely used [1, 2].

Taking into account the above and the solution to this problem, we have developed an experimental sample of a potato digger for a walk-behind tractor to perform agricultural technological processes for growing

vegetables and potatoes on small-circuit land and household plots of farmer and farm enterprises that most fully meet the agricultural conditions of the Republic [3, 4, 5].

A potato digger is a structure consisting of a body, a conveyor, a knife (ripper), lugs, a wheel axle and conveyor shafts. In front of the case, there is a rack with which the potato digger is attached to walk-behind tractors of various models. On the side walls, there are holes for fastening and adjusting the knife, as well as holes with plain bearings for installing the conveyor shaft and wheel axle. The wheel axle has holes for positioning and fastening the lugs and a gear wheel for transmitting torque through the gear to the conveyor shaft. On the conveyor shaft, there are sprockets that

engage with the conveyor bars, thereby setting it in motion. Optimum tension of the conveyor is achieved with the help of a tensioner and a driven shaft, which is installed in the grooves of the housing [6, 7].

Experimental studies were carried out jointly with four organizations: KXMITI, OAO "BMKB-Agromash", UzGCITT and the Research Institute of Vegetables, Melons and Potatoes (NIIOBKiK).

The tasks of the research included the determination of agrotechnical indicators (losses and damage to potato tubers) of the work of a potato digger. In the tests, the qualitative indicators of the potato digger were studied. The figure shows the process of operation of a potato digger (picture.).

Pic. Type of potato digger in the workflow

Characteristics of the test conditions are given in table.1, and the test results were processed and summarized in table. 2 and 3.

According to the program, the following indicators were determined during the testing process:

- degree of soil separation;
- loss and damage of tubers;
- traction resistance of the potato digger;

- fuel consumption.

The results obtained in the tests are shown in tables 2-3.

The test results show (Table 2) that at the tested speeds, the degree of soil separation in the experimental energy-saving potato digger was 79.8-83.8%. This is ensured by the destruction of soil clods by support-clod breaking devices.

Table 1

Characteristic conditions holding tests

№	Name indicators	Meaning indicators
1	Time tests	June 2022
2	Variety potatoes	Santa
3	The biological yield of tubers, t/ha	19,6
4	State haulm	semi-dry
5	Height comb, cm	19,4
6	Maximum tuber depth, cm	Nineteen
7	Width spacing, cm	70
8	Microrelief	Weakly expressed
9	Soil type and mechanical composition	Serozem, medium-heavy loamy
10	Relief	Smooth
11	Soil moisture by layers (sm), %:	
	0-10	14,9
	10-20	15,5
12	20-30	17,3
	Soil hardness by layers (sm), MPa:	
	0-10	0,9 4
	10-20	1,4 1
	20-30	1,9 2

The data of Table 2 show that the use of an energy-saving potato digger increases the completeness of potato harvesting by 5.2-7.2% and reduces damage to tubers by 5.5-8.8% due to the destruction of hard soil lumps and minimal digging of the potato layer before transferring them on separating organs, as well as intensive separation in the main soil elevator and laying potato tubers with a minimum fall height.

Table 2

Agrotechnical performance indicators of the compared potato diggers for soil separation

Indicators	Serial potato digger		Experimental potato digger	
	Unit movement speed, m/ s	0,4	0,8	0,4
Degree separation soil, %	69,3	64,1	83,8	80,2
Completeness of digging out tubers, %:	10,8	8,6	3,6	3,1
Damage tubers, %, by mass	7,8	9,2	2,3	2,6

The results of processing the obtained data show (Table 3) that the traction resistance of an energy-saving potato digger is 19-21% less compared to a serial potato digger. This is explained by the fact that the side disks of the experimental support-clod breaking device cut the slopes of the potato bed (the zone of greatest resistance) and thereby reduce the resistance of the cut tuberous soil layer when it is lifted to the elevators, and

also reduce the amount of soil entering the main elevator of the machine.

In addition, when passing along the crest, elastic rods with a roller destroy the surface layer of the potato bed and the soil clods lying on it.

Further, the reduced sectional plowshares dig out the rest of the potato bed, as a result of which the loading of the working bodies is reduced.

Table 3

Energy performance of compared potato diggers

Indicators	potato digger	
	Serial potato digger	Experimental energy-saving potato digger
Travel speed, m/ s	0.4 0.8	0.6 1.0
Traction resistance, kN	1, 1 1, 3	0.75 1.10

To take the minimum amount of soil mass, the width of the intermediate share is smaller compared to the width of the main shares, and it is located in the row spacing. During operation, the intermediate plowshare does not dig out the side zone of the potato bed and the zone between the rows with the highest density, but only picks up the fallen tubers from the row spacing and directs them toward the main elevator. The main plowshares dig only that part of the ridge in which the potato tubers are placed.

Further, the soil transferred to the elevator with the help of wavy rippers is destroyed, most of it is sifted out, and the tubers and the remaining soil are fed to the swather, where the remaining part of the soil is sifted, with the help of the swather the potato tubers on the ground are collected in a heap.

The advantages of the proposed energy-saving potato digger are that the use of these working bodies reduces the flow of excess soil along with lumps on the separating working bodies, thereby reducing the loading of working bodies, improving soil separation, reducing the loss and damage of tubers, labor costs, as well as traction resistance.

From the data of Table 2, it can be seen that during digging, losses and damage to tubers are reduced due to the destruction of hard soil lumps and minimal digging of the soil of the potato layer before transferring it to the separating organs, as well as due to intensive separation at the main elevator. These indicators meet the requirements of the TOR.

The advantages of the proposed potato digger lies in the fact that the use of the recommended parameters reduces the metal consumption, reduces their loading

and labor costs, losses and damage to potato tubers, and improves the quality of work.

Conclusion

The results of field tests in the experimental farm showed that the agrotechnical performance of the tested potato digger meets the agrotechnical requirements. The development of a potato digger for digging up potatoes on small-cultivated land plots of farms and dekhkan farms eliminates labor costs and solves problems in this industry.

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PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING TECHNICAL TOOLS FOR GROWING AND HARVESTING POTATOES

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Abstract

The cultivation and harvesting of potatoes is traditionally based on single-machine units, which is accompanied by multiple passes of equipment across the field, an increase in material and labor costs. The article presents the development prospects for the development of multifunctional units with a combined mounted and multi-threaded use of engine power. Due to the use of combined units, increased functionality of individual machines that are part of these units, the labor costs of machine operators, field workers in the main and auxiliary operations, as well as the consumption of fuel and lubricants, are significantly reduced.

Keywords. Potato growing, tiller, potato digger, energy intensity, resource-saving, front mounted machines, combined units.

The potato is the fourth largest food in the world after wheat, corn and rice. As a valuable source of high-quality protein, vitamins, minerals and carbohydrates, potatoes are one of the main food of plant origin for humans in some countries.

Growing and harvesting potatoes is an important part of the agricultural industry of the Republic for providing the population of the Republic with potatoes of its own production, while much attention is paid to the development of a complex of modern highly efficient and resource-saving technical means that ensure the cultivation and digging of potatoes with minimal energy consumption. The Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 outlines “...further strengthening of the country's food security, expanding the production of environmentally friendly products, a significant increase in the export potential of the agricultural sector; optimization of areas for growing potatoes and other vegetable crops by reducing land plots intended for cotton and wheat. To accomplish these tasks, it is necessary to develop a set of machines for growing and harvesting potatoes, which ensures the required quality of work in the soil and climatic conditions of our Republic

with minimal energy consumption, this will reduce imports due to the localization of production, which is one of the important tasks [1].

The pace of development of potato growing should make it possible to fully meet the needs of the population for this product. Currently, the production of potatoes in farms is characterized by high labor costs, monetary and material resources. This is explained by the absence of certain types of machines, and the existing technologies for cultivating and harvesting potatoes are traditionally based on single machine units, which is accompanied by multiple passes of heavy equipment across the field, an increase in material and labor costs and agrotechnical terms of work.

The solution to the problem of reducing labor and resource costs is possible by modernizing existing standard technologies for growing potatoes and using specialized multifunctional multi-machine units in potato growing that perform two or more technological operations in one pass through the field, using a number of new machines that improve the efficiency of the industry.

Based on the results of the analysis of patent information materials of foreign experience, it was found